

Book History – A Link between Information Science and Humanities

The Value of Information Contained in Book-Sellers Catalogues

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Abstract

This poster is briefly presenting the results of research that the author completed as part of her PhD theses. The research included analysis of 8 book-sellers catalogues published in Zagreb, Croatia, between 1796 and 1823. The large amount of data extracted from the catalogues enables insight into the book-trade in Zagreb at that time. This data informs us about the books that were available for the reading audience in Zagreb, in terms of languages and script the books were printed in, places they were published at and were imported from. The variety of genres speaks about the book-sellers ability to cater for a variety of interests of local readers, including local professionals and scholars. The information on book-prices and discounts allows for conclusions on the buying power and also offers at least a partial business perspective of book-sellers as traders and managers. Other aspects of book-sellers' work, such as classification, standardization, orthography, printing practices, etc. can also be discussed based on information from the analysed catalogues.

Keywords: Book-seller catalogue, Book history, Zagreb, Book trade

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1 Introduction

This poster is briefly presenting the results of research that the author completed as part of her PhD theses. The research was performed on 8 book-sellers catalogues published in Zagreb, Croatia, between 1796 and 1823. All 9939 titles of books listed in these catalogues were entered into a database, followed by the price, language, script, place of publishing, book-seller's remarks and any other information about the books that were included by the author of the catalogue. This enabled statistical analysis and the evidence-based conclusions on the book-trade in Zagreb at that time.

2 Concept of the poster

The intention of this poster is not to focus on the research results themselves but to put them in the perspective of different academic disciplines. A book catalogue, be it library or publisher's catalogue, is usually perceived as a potential topic of research in library or information science. However, this research proves that a quantitative analysis of a historical book catalogue can be equally interesting for many disciplines.

The poster will be made in the form of a concept map, presenting the information from book-sellers catalogues, with the emphasis on the value of this information for information science and for other disciplines, particularly humanities. The following concepts will be presented, showing groups of information and fields of research they can contribute to.

- Classification systems used in the 8 catalogues and the comparison to other systems that were in use;
- Book genre, range of genres available for the reading audience in Zagreb – contribution to local literary and reception history and history of science;
- Language and script of listed books – contribution to historical research of Zagreb as a multilingual and multicultural community;
- Place of publishing – links between Zagreb and cultural centers around Europe, relation between local production and import;
- Prices and discounts, the buying power and the business of selling books – potential contribution to economic history;

- Orthography, standardization, printing practices – contribution to printing history. How difficult it must have been to create a catalogue!